

Appendix 5.2: Main features of the pathway studies

(A) Main features for global pathway studies analysed. Terminology for narratives and pathways from 5.5.2. Stakeholder engagement: — : none, o: limited, ●: participatory process, ★: participatory process with indigenous and local knowledge (ILK), nd: no data; Exploratory scenarios: ●: present or referred to in the pathway study.

Narrative	Pathway	Scale	Sector	Actors	Year of pathway	Stakeholders / ILK	Exploratory scenarios	Reference
Green economy	Innovation	Global	Cross-sector	Private	2050	★		(WBCSD, 2010)
Green economy	Innovation	Global	Agriculture	Multiple		●		(WEF, 2010)
Green economy	Innovation	Global	Agriculture	Int.Org.	2050	nd		(FAO, 2014)
Green economy	Innovation	Global	Agriculture	Int.Org.	2050	—		(FAO, 2009)
Green economy	Innovation	Global	Water	Multiple	2050	o		(United Nations World Water Assessment Programme, 2015)
Green economy	Innovation	Global	Water	Multiple	2025	★		(Cosgrove & Rijsberman, 2014)
Green economy	Land sharing	Global	Cross- sector	NGO	2025	●		(Wetlands International, 2015)
Green economy	Land sharing	Global	Cross-sector	Int.Org.	2024	●		(Ramsar Convention Secretariat, 2016)
Green economy	nd	Global	Fisheries	Multiple	2030	o		(CASS, 2008)
Low Carbon	Innovation	Global	Energy	Multiple	2030	—		(Ki-moon, 2011; WB, 2012)
Low Carbon	Innovation	Global	Energy	NGO	2050	o	●	(Olesen, Kvetny, & la Rovere, 2002)
Low Carbon	Innovation	Global	Energy	Multiple	2050	—	●	(WWF/Ecofys/OMA, 2011)
Low Carbon	Innovation	Global	Energy	Multiple	2050		●	(IPCC, 2012)
Transition Movements	Resource sparing	Global	Cross-sector	NGO	2050	★	●	(Greenpeace, 2009)

Narrative	Pathway	Scale	Sector	Actors	Year of pathway	Stakeholders / ILK	Exploratory scenarios	Reference
Transition Movements	Resource sparing	Global	Cross-sector	Academic	2020	—		(Kates & Clark, 1999)
Transition Movements	Resource sparing	Global	Energy	Academic	2050	-		(van Vuuren et al., 2012)
Transition Movements	Resource sparing	Global	Energy	Multiple	2050	●	●	(WBGU, 2011)
Transition Movements	Capabilities	Global	Water	Multiple	2030	●		(FAO, 2015; Groundwater Governance, 2015)
Transition Movements	Capabilities	Global	Water	NGO	2020	nd		(WaterAid, 2013)

(B) Main features for European scale pathway studies analysed. Terminology for narratives and pathways from 5.5.2. Stakeholder engagement: — : none, ○ : limited, ● : participatory process, ★ : participatory process with ILK, nd: no data; Exploratory scenarios: ● : present or referred to in the pathway study.

Narrative	Pathway	Scale	Sector	Actor	Year of pathway	Stakeholders / ILK	Exploratory scenarios	Reference
Green Economy	Innovation	Europe	Cross-sector	Int.Org.	2030	●		(BECOTEPS, 2011)
Green Economy	Innovation	Europe	Agriculture	Int.Org.	2030	★	●	(Barabanova, Zanoli, Schlüter, & Stopes, 2015)
Green Economy	Innovation	Europe	Forestry	Int.Org.	2030	●		(The Forest-based Sector ETP, 2013)
Green Economy	Innovation	Europe	Fisheries	Int.Org.	2030	●	●	(EATIP, 2012)
Green Economy	Innovation	Europe	Agriculture	Int.Org.	2030	●		(Maggio, van Criekinge, & Malingreau, 2015)
Green Economy	Land sparing	Europe	Environment	NGO	2023	●		(Sylvén & Widstrand, 2013)
Green Economy	Land sparing	Europe	Cross-sector	Int.Org.	2050	●	●	(Pedroli, Rounsevell, Metzger, Paterson, & The VOLANTE Consortium, 2015); see visions in (Pérez-Soba, M., Paterson, J., Metzger, 2015)
Green Economy	Land sparing	Europe	Environment	Int. Org.	2050	●		(van Zeijts et al., 2017)
Green Economy	Land sharing	Europe	Cross-sector	Int.Org.	2050	●	●	(Pedroli et al., 2015); see visions in (Pérez-Soba, M., Paterson, J., Metzger, 2015)
Green Economy	Land sharing	Europe	Agriculture	Academic	2030	●	●	(McKee & Holstead, 2014)
Green Economy	Land sharing	Europe	Agriculture	Int.Org.	2030	●		(Food Drink Europe, 2012)
Green Economy	Land sharing	Europe	Environment	Int.Org.	2050	●		(EC, 2011)
Green Economy	Land sharing	Europe	Forestry	Int.Org.	2020	—		(Forest Europe, 2011)

Narrative	Pathway	Scale	Sector	Actor	Year of pathway	Stakeholders / ILK	Exploratory scenarios	Reference
Green Economy	Land sharing	Europe	Environment	Int. Org.	2050	●		(van Zeijts et al., 2017)
Low Carbon	Innovation	Europe	Energy	Int.Org.	2030	●		(EC, 2006)
Low Carbon	Regional multifunctionality	Europe	Cross-sector	Academic	2050	—		(Netherlands Environmental Assessment Agency & Stockholm Resilience Centre, 2009)
Ecotopian	Local multifunctionality	Europe	Cross-sector	Int.Org.	2050	●	●	(Pedroli, Rounsevell, Metzger, Paterson, & The VOLANTE Consortium, 2015); see visions in (Pérez-Soba, M., Paterson, J., Metzger, 2015)
Transition Movements	Resource sparing	Europe	Agriculture	Int.Org.	2030	✱	●	(Barabanova et al., 2015)
Transition Movements	Resource sparing	Europe	Environment	Academic	2050	●	●	(van Vliet & Kok, 2015)
Transition Movements	Resource sparing	Europe	Cross-sector	Academic	2050	●		(Mont, Neuvonen, & Lähteenoja, 2014)
Transition Movements	Resource sparing	Europe	Environment	Int.Org.	2030	●	●	(UNEP/UNECE, 2016)
Transition Movements	Resource sparing	Europe	Environment	Int. Org.	2050	●		(van Zeijts et al., 2017)

(C) Main features for Eastern Europe and Central Asia pathway studies analysed. Terminology for narratives and pathways from 5.5.2. Stakeholder engagement: — : none, ○: limited, ●: participatory process, ✳: participatory process with ILK, nd: no data; Exploratory scenarios: ●: present or referred to in the pathway study.

Narrative	Pathway	Scale	Sector	Actor	Year of pathway	Stakeholders / ILK	Exploratory scenarios	Reference
Green economy	Innovation	Russia	Cross-sector	Government	2030			(Ministry of Economic Development of the Russian Federation, 2013)
Green economy	Land sparing	Ukraine	NBSAP	Government	2020			(Parliament of Ukraine, 2016)
Green economy	Land sharing (?)	Belarus	NBSAP	Government	2030			(Council of Ministers of the Republic of Belarus, 2015a)
Green economy	Land sharing (?)	Belarus	NBSAP	Government	2020			(Council of Ministers of the Republic of Belarus, 2015a)
Green economy	nd	Georgia	NBSAP	Government	2020			(Ministry of Environment and Natural Resources Protection of Georgia, 2014)
Green economy	nd	Kyrgyzstan	NBSAP	Government	2024			(Ministry of Environmental Protection of Kyrgyzstan, 1998)
Green economy	nd	Turkmenistan	NBSAP	Government	Open			(Ministry of Nature Protection of Turkmenistan, 2002)
Green economy	nd	Armenia	NBSAP	Government	2020			(Ministry for Nature Protection of Armenia, 1999)
Green economy	nd	Russia	NBSAP	Government	2020			(Ministry of Natural Resources and Environment of the Russian Federation, 2014)
Green economy	Innovation	Azerbaijan	NBSAP	Government	2020			(President of the Republic of Azerbaijan, 2017)

Narrative	Pathway	Scale	Sector	Actor	Year of pathway	Stakeholders / ILK	Exploratory scenarios	Reference
Green economy	nd	Tajikistan	NBSAP	Government	2020			(National Centre for Biodiversity and Biosecurity of the Republic of Tajikistan, 2016)
Green economy	nd	Moldova	NBSAP	Government	2020			(Government of the Republic of Moldova, 2015)
Green economy	nd	Kazakhstan	Cross-sector	Government	2050			(President of the Republic of Kazakhstan, 2012)
Green economy	nd	Uzbekistan	Cross-sector	Government	2050			(State Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan on Nature Protection, 2012)
Green economy	nd	Belarus	Cross-sector	Government	2030			(Council of Ministers of the Republic of Belarus, 2015b)

(D) Main features for local pathway studies analysed. Terminology for narratives and pathways from 5.5.2. Stakeholder engagement: — : none, o: limited, ●: participatory process, ★: participatory process with ILK, nd: no data; Exploratory scenarios: ●: present or referred to in the pathway study.

Narrative	Pathway	Scale	Sector	Actors	Year of pathway	Stakeholders / ILK	Exploratory scenarios	Reference
Green economy	Innovation	Local (Seyhan Basin, Turkey)	Environment	Academic	2030	●	●	(Cakmak et al., 2010)
Green economy	Land sharing	Local (Biscay, Spain)	Cross-sector	Academic	2050	●	●	(Palacios-Agundez, Casado-Arzuaga, Madariaga, & Onaindia, 2013)
Transition movements	Capabilities	Local (Transylvania, Romania)	Cross-sector	Academic	2042	●	●	(Hanspach et al., 2014)
Green economy	Land sharing	Local (Vispatal, Valais, Switzerland)	Cross-sector	Academic	2040	●	●	(Brunner, Huber, & Grêt-Regamey, 2015)
Transition movements	Resource sparing	Local (Spain)	Agriculture	Academic	2030	★	●	(Oteros-Rozas, Martín-López, López, Palomo, & González, 2013)
Transition movements	Resource sparing	Local (Finland)	Agriculture	Academic	2030	●	●	(Kirveenummi, Mäkelä, & Saarimaa, 2013)
Green economy	Innovation	Local (Doñana, Spain)	Environment	Academic	2035	●	●	(Palomo, Martín-López, Lopez-Santiago, & Montes, 2011)
Ecotopian solutions	Innovation	Local (Barcelona, Spain)	Agriculture; Urban planning	Academic	NA	●	●	(Cerón-Palma, Sanyé-Mengual, Oliver-Solà, Montero, & Rieradevall, 2012)
Ecotopian solutions	Innovation	Local (Sweden)	Urban planning	Academic	2050	●	●	(Svenfelt, Engstrom, & Svane, 2011)

Narrative	Pathway	Scale	Sector	Actors	Year of pathway	Stakeholders / ILK	Exploratory scenarios	Reference
Ecotopian solutions	Innovation	Local (Stockholm, Sweden)	Urban planning	Academic	2050	●	●	(Höjer, Gullberg, & Pettersson, 2011)
Transition movements	Resource sparing	Local	Forestry	Academic		*		(Beland Lindahl, Sandström, & Sténs, 2016)
Transition Movements	Resource sparing	Local (London, UK)	Urban planning; Agriculture	Academic	NA	●	●	(Eames & Egmore, 2011)
Transition movements	Capabilities	Local (Doñana, Spain)	Environment	Academic	2035	●	●	(Palomo, Martín-López, Lopez-Santiago, & Montes, 2011)

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